

Investigation on Variability of Whipping in Irregular Wave Conditions for a Large Container Ship

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Abstract. The ability to assess whipping responses and increase of vertical wave bending are both especially important to evaluation of hull girder strength of large container ships. Whipping occurs when slamming pressure acts on the bow flare, and tank tests and numerical investigations have been carried out by many researchers but there has been little benchmark test data, especially data focusing on the statistical characteristics of whipping response in irregular waves for large container ships, published to date. The authors conducted multiple tank tests focusing on irregular wave conditions in which waves were generated with one wave condition varied in order to observe the statistical characteristics. Furthermore, three kinds of bow flare were prepared to investigate the effects of bow flare shape, and the bow section was replaced like lego blocks so that change in whipping response could be investigated. Many pressure gauges were also arranged around the bow so as to observe the relationship between the whipping responses and the pressures acting on the bow flares. As a result, mean value of the whipping coefficient f_{whip} , which was introduced as an index for assessing whipping response, was less dependent on the bow flare shape, and a comparison of results with experiments and simulations showed that the M_w , M_{whip} , and f_{whip} in hogging agreed well. Instead of using the mean value of the whipping coefficient, vertical wave bending moment was observed for each data group, but it was difficult to identify clearly difference of short-term whipping responses depending on the flare type.

Keywords: Whipping, Container ship, Tank test, Bow flare slamming

1. Introduction

The ability of assess whipping response in large container ships is especially important to evaluating hull girder strength, which is the most important with respect to hull structural strength. Unlike oil tankers and bulk carriers, container ships, in general, have large bow flare shape, with slamming pressure acting on the bow flare occurring in rough weather, and this leads to a whipping response and an increase in vertical wave bending moment [1][2].

Since an increase in the vertical wave bending moment may directly lead to collapse of the hull and is a critical event, many researchers have been carrying out investigations based upon sea-keeping tank tests and numerical simulations [3][4][5]. Although numerical simulations, such as potential-basis codes considering the effect of slamming and CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) can estimate whipping response so that the characteristics of an individual vessel are reflected, it is well known the whipping response obtained from such codes varies widely even under the same calculation conditions. For this reason, some researchers have worked on studies based on benchmark tests focusing on the whipping response to investigate any differences [6][7][8].

Where the numerical simulation of irregular waves has been conducted, the calculation results differ even under when the same wave condition such as mean wave period, significant wave height, and wave angle were the same since the details of each generated wave depend on used random numbers with respect to the phase of the wave components. It is, therefore, adequate for reasonable hull structural designs to conduct multiple calculations in each wave condition by changing such generated waves. Although the aim of conducting many tank tests is, in general, to verify numerical codes, there has been little benchmark test data, especially data focusing on the statistical characteristics of the whipping response in irregular waves for large container ships, published to date. That is, there is no repeated measurements under the same wave condition (the same short-term sea state). With this in mind, this study involved, sea-keeping tank tests using a large container ship model called NK-14KTEU that focused on irregular wave conditions to measure whipping response in which multiple tests were conducted

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with a single wave condition being varied for the generated waves so as to observe statistical characteristics. Furthermore, three kinds of bow flare were prepared to investigate the effect of bow flare shape, and the bow section was replaced like lego blocks to investigate the change in whipping response. Lastly, many pressure gauges were arranged around the bow so as to observe the relationship between the whipping responses and the pressures acting on the bow flares.

2. Tank tests

2.1. 14,000TEU container ship model with backbone

NK-14KTEU, a 14,000TEU container ship, was used for tank tests. Table 1 shows the main particulars of the ship, and the parameters shown in the table assume full load condition. Figure 1 shows the offset data, with the shape of bow flare being referred to as “middle type” hereinafter. In addition to the middle type, the authors prepared two other bow flare shapes, “large type” and “small type” as shown in Figure 2, to the extent that they were also possible hull structural designs. The hull shape with the middle type is the same as that used in the authors’ previous studies [9][10].

A model ship scaled at 1/64 (Model ship $L_{PP} = 5.5\text{ m}$) was divided into eight parts connected by two backbones, as shown in Figure 3. Strain gauge sensors were installed in the divided cross sections at S.S. 1.5, 3.0, 4.0, 5.1, 6.0, 7.0, and 8.5 on the backbones so as to measure the strain at four points in each cross section. Vertical wave bending moments were obtained from measured strain data based on a three-point bending test carried out in advance. Table 2 shows the natural frequencies of the model ship with the backbones, obtained from hammering tests.

Table 1. Main particulars of NK-14KTEU

	Model scale	Full scale
Length overall, L_{oa} [m]	5.786	370.3
Length between perpendicular, L_{pp} [m]	5.500	352.0
Breadth, B [m]	0.781	50.0
Depth, D [m]	0.469	30.0
Draft, d [m]	0.234	15.0
Block factor, C_b	0.676	0.676
KG [m] (Center of gravity from keel)	0.328	21.0
Kyy [m] (Radius of gyration around the Y-axis)	1.375	88.0

Figure 1. Hull form of NK-14KTEU

Figure 2. Bow flare shapes of middle, large, and small type at S.S. 9.75

Figure 3. Container ship model with two backbones

Table 2. Natural frequencies obtained by hammering tests

Mode	Natural frequency (Wet) [Hz]	
	Model scale	Full scale
2-node	3.5	0.438
3-node	5.4	0.675
4-node	7.2	0.90

Any of the three types of bow flare shapes mentioned above could be installed forward of S.S. 8.5 in the model ship, ten or more fiber bragg grating (FBG) type sensors [11] are attached each at S.S. 9.0, 9.5, 9.75, and 10.0 in order to measure pressure acting on the bow as shown in Figures 4 and 5. In addition strain gauge sensors were also attached but the number of sensors was less than the FBG sensors: five sensors at S.S. 9.0 and three sensors at S.S. 9.5.

Figure 4. Bow of model ship and pressure sensors

Figure 5. FBG sensors at S.S. 9.0 (left), strain gauge sensors at S.S. 9.0 (right)

2.2. Test conditions

Tank tests were carried out in the head sea condition at ship speed of *5 knots* in a large towing tank (length $220.0\text{ m} \times$ width $14.0\text{ m} \times$ depth 6.5 m) at the Akishima Laboratory in Japan. This paper describes some experimental results in a representative condition (a significant wave height of 12 m , and a zero-crossing mean wave period of 11.5 s) for the observation of statistical characteristics of the whipping response. This wave period and wave height were decided based upon the RAO of the vertical wave bending moment at midship using linear sea-keeping analysis and the results of statistical prediction, which reproduce the extreme value of the vertical wave bending moment, according to the method to identify the short-term sea state found by Kawabe et al [12]. Irregular waves were generated with random phases based upon the Pierson-Moskowitz wave spectra. Under these conditions, towing tests were repeatedly performed so that the number of vertical wave bending moments cycles was about 1000. The exact number of waves and vertical wave bending moment cycles are shown in Table 3. In the original bow flare (middle type), irregular waves based on eight random numbers were generated separately, whereas those based on three random numbers were used in the large type and small type, i.e. the tank tests were conducted in around $1000\text{ cycles} \times 8$ times for the middle type and around $1000\text{ cycles} \times 3$ times each for the large and small type.

Table 3. The number of waves and vertical wave bending moments

		Wave	VBM
Middle type	Group 1	1135	1003
	Group 2	1129	1012
	Group 3	1087	997
	Group 4	1001	876
	Group 5	1112	995
	Group 6	998	864
	Group 7	993	865

	Group 8	983	864
Large type	Group 1	1314	1155
	Group 2	1138	1013
	Group 3	1141	1005
	Group 1	1276	1139
Small type	Group 2	1152	997
	Group 3	1146	997

3. Results of tank tests in irregular wave conditions

This section investigates the effect of bow flare type on whipping response in terms of statistical analysis with tank test data in irregular wave conditions. To evaluate whipping effect from tank test data, the analysis was carried out according to the following procedure based upon a previous study [13].

- 1) Separate time series data of vertical wave bending moment obtained from the strain data into rigid component and elastic component (component due to whipping) including rigid component by low-pass filter.
- 2) Obtain the maximum and minimum values of both component for each wave by zero-up crossing analysis for low-passed data.
- 3) Estimate two parameters of the Weibull distribution by least squares method based on the top 20 % data, and fit exceedance probability distribution.
- 4) Determine the rigid component M_w and the elastic component M_{whip} with an exceedance probability of 10^{-3} and then obtain the ratio of M_{whip} to M_w as the whipping factor, that is $f_{whip} = M_{whip} / M_w$.

Figure 6 presents the exceedance probability distribution of the vertical wave bending moment in hogging and sagging at S.S. 5.1 for around 1000 cycles \times 8 times derived from procedures 1 to 4 above for the middle type. The exceedance probability distributions for the small and large bow flare types were obtained from 1000 cycles \times 3 times tests in the same wave condition, as shown in Figures 7 and 8. The value of vertical wave bending moment is dimensionless using density ρ , gravitational acceleration g , significant wave amplitude $\zeta_s (= 0.5H_s)$, breadth B , and length between perpendicular L_{pp} . It was observed that the vertical wave bending moment varies to some extent even under the same sea conditions because of the difference of the details of each wave, i.e. the difference of the random number for wave creation. Figure 9 shows the average value of M_w , M_{whip} (bars) with each value (plots) and average whipping factor f_{whip} and each value in hogging, and Figure 10 shows those in sagging. Although bow flare type did not cause a significant difference in M_w , M_{whip} , and f_{whip} in hogging, M_{whip} and f_{whip} of the large type showed differences in sagging compared to the middle and small types.

Figure 6. Exceedance probability of vertical wave bending moment at S.S. 5.1 (bow flare: middle type)

Figure 7. Exceedance probability of vertical wave bending moment at S.S. 5.1 (bow flare: small type)

Figure 8. Exceedance probability of vertical wave bending moment at S.S. 5.1 (bow flare: large type)

Figure 9. Average M_w , M_{whip} , and f_{whip} in hogging

Figure 10. Average M_w , M_{whip} , and f_{whip} in sagging

4. Comparison with experimental results and numerical simulation

In the numerical simulation, the authors used a non-linear 3-dimensional potential code developed by ClassNK (referred to as 3-DPM.WHIP hereinafter), which takes the non-linearity of Froude-Krylov force and restoring force into account. This code is based upon a non-linear code which was used in a previous research [14], with a function to estimate slamming force based on GWM (Generalized Wagner model) and a function to calculate elastic vibrations with a Timoshenko beam model by mode analysis being added [15][16].

This comparative study was addressed using the model ship with the middle type. Eight-times simulations were carried out in the same irregular wave condition to obtain the rigid and elastic component of the vertical wave bending moment at midship. For the rigid mode simulation, slamming force was not included into hydrodynamic forces. Figures 11 and 12 respectively illustrate the exceedance probability for both component with a 95 % confidence interval by the experiment and numerical simulation for the model ship of the middle bow flare type. The exceedance probability distribution of the simulation tended to be consistent with that of the experiment. Although there are some variations in the elastic components by the numerical simulation, average M_w , M_{whip} and f_{whip} in hogging were in good agreement, as shown in Figure 13. As for sagging, some discrepancies between the calculation and experiment were observed in average M_{whip} and f_{whip} compared to hogging as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 11. Exceedance probability of vertical wave bending moment at S.S. 5.1 by the experiment for middle type

Figure 12. Exceedance probability of vertical bending moment at S.S. 5.0 by the calculation for middle type

Figure 13. Comparison between experiments and calculations regarding average M_w , M_{whip} , and whipping factor f_{whip} in hogging

Figure 14. Exceedance probability of vertical bending moment at S.S. 5.0 by the calculation for middle type

5. Discussion

In the previous section, the average whipping coefficient f_{whip} is being used as an index to capture the effect of whipping response. In order to investigate the cause of the tendency of the coefficients, the authors compared the results of experiments of the middle, large, and small bow flare types with respect to the measured values of ship motion and hydrodynamic pressure in addition to vertical wave bending moment. Figures 15 to 18 show the comparison of the time history of the three bow flare type's experiments, in which waves were generated using the same signal. These figures show time series of 50 seconds each, and show vertical wave bending moments with whipping response, pitch, hydrodynamic pressure acting on the bottom at S.S. 9.0, and the pressure acting on bow flare of S.S. 9.5 (the measurement point corresponding to the number "04" height position in Figure 5).

It was found that pitch shows almost the same behavior regardless of bow flare type, and the hydrodynamic pressure acting on the bottom of S.S. 9.0, where the hull is always submerged, also shows almost the same value. Therefore, the ship motions and the hydrodynamic pressures below the water surface can be considered to contribute to the vertical wave bending moment at the same level in any tank test. Moreover, it can be judged that both wave creation are also adequately controlled.

It was also observed that the pressure acting on the bow flare of S.S. 9.5 shows different behavior depending on the flare type, and it was also confirmed that the pressure of the bow flare triggers the whipping response in some parts of the time history. However, when the bow flare pressure of one flare type becomes larger than that of the other flare type, the whipping response does not necessarily have the same magnitude relationship, and it is difficult to find a trend difference from these figures. It will, therefore, be necessary to observe the trend difference using the time series data which add up the measured values of all the pressure sensors above the waterline instead of the pinpoint pressure. In addition, depending on the timing of slamming, which acts during the whipping by a slamming, it is expected that the whipping may be amplified or weakened, and it is also necessary to observe. But they will be the subject of a future study.

Next, unlike the previous section, we observed the relationship between M_w and M_{whip} for around 1,000 cycles, not M_w and M_{whip} as average. In other words, we observed the relationship between M_w and M_{whip} for eight middle-type case, and the relationship between M_w and M_{whip} for three large-type and the small-type cases each. Figure 19 plots the experimental M_w on the horizontal axis, and the difference between the experimental M_{whip} and M_w on the vertical axis. Figure 20 shows the relationship of bow flare angles on horizontal plane with the difference between the experimental M_{whip} and M_w , and the value of the horizontal axis is the angle between the line connecting the 16.5 m height position and the 25.0 m height position in full scale (that is, the line connecting "05" and "02" in Figure 5) and the horizontal plane. As in Figure 9, these values are dimensionless. Figures 19 and 20 may show some differences in trend depending on the flare type, but it is difficult to quantify the convergence of short-term whipping responses, and a systematic investigation by more tank tests, e.g. more than ten times 1,000 cycles, will be necessary, for example in a similar approach with reference [17].

Figure 15. Time history, of 20 to 70 seconds, for vertical wave bending moment with whipping (top), pitch (second), pressure acting on the bottom at S.S. 9.0 (third), and pressure acting on bow flare at S.S. 9.5 (bottom)

Figure 16. Time history, of 70 to 120 seconds, for vertical wave bending moment with whipping (top), pitch (second), and pressure acting on the bottom at S.S. 9.0 (third), and pressure acting on bow flare at S.S. 9.5 (bottom)

Figure 17. Time history, of 120 to 170 seconds, for vertical wave bending moment with whipping (top), pitch (second), and pressure acting on the bottom at S.S. 9.0 (third), and pressure acting on bow flare at S.S. 9.5 (bottom)

Figure 18. Time history, of 170 to 220 seconds, for vertical wave bending moment with whipping (top), pitch (second), and pressure acting on the bottom at S.S. 9.0 (third), and pressure acting on bow flare at S.S. 9.5 (bottom)

Figure 19. Relationship of M_w and difference between M_{whip} and M_w in each experiment

Figure 20. Relationship of bow flare angle on horizontal plane and difference between M_{whip} and M_w in each experiment

6. Conclusions

Benchmark tank tests were conducted to obtain the statistical characteristics of the whipping response using a 14,000 TEU container ship model (NK-14KTEU) with a backbone. Multiple tank tests were repeated under the same irregular wave condition. In addition, three types of bow flare were prepared, and the effect on the whipping response was examined.

The whipping coefficient, which is the ratio of vertical wave bending moment with whipping to the moment without whipping, was used as an evaluation index in accordance with the procedure established by past research. It was suggested that the mean value of the whipping coefficient f_{whip} was less dependent on the bow flare shape, and a comparison of results with experiments and numerical simulations showed that the M_w , M_{whip} , and f_{whip} in hogging agreed well.

When the relationship between the measured values of pressure and ship motion as well as vertical wave bending moment including whipping was observed, the pressure acting on the bow flare was influenced by the difference of bow flare type, but there was little correlation between the measured value of pressure at one point and the whipping response.

Instead of using the mean value of the whipping coefficient, the relationship between M_w , M_{whip} was observed for each data group of 1,000 cycles, and it is observed bow flare shape may have a few effects on the whipping response when the short-term sea conditions encountered are the same, but it is difficult to quantify the convergence of short-term whipping responses, and a systematic investigation by more tank tests will be necessary.

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